

KNOWLEDGE
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Digital Ecosystems for Sustainable Digitalisation of Farming

HIGHLIGHTS REPORT

6 FEBRUARY 2025

Introduction

On 6 February 2025, CODECS hosted its third [Knowledge Accelerator](#) webinar, focusing on [Digital Ecosystems for Sustainable Digitalisation of Farming](#). Organised by the [European Association for Innovation in Local Development \(AEIDL\)](#), the event brought together over 100 experts from the EU and beyond to explore how integrated digital systems can empower farmers and rural communities, moving beyond the limitations of isolated tools. With more than 200 registrations, the webinar attracted a diverse audience, including rural practitioners, end-users, researchers, and policymakers.

Serafin Pazos Vidal from the European Association for Innovation in Local Development (AEIDL) welcomed participants and introduced the webinar's objectives. In his opening remarks, he noted that the webinar would explore how effective digital ecosystems can facilitate the digital transition in agriculture, creating an environment that fosters resilience and productivity. Digital transition in agriculture requires more than technology and that a digital ecosystem is a space where data, tools, and expertise come together to drive sustainable digitisation of farming.

ORGANISER:

6 FEBRUARY 2025

ONLINE

104 PARTICIPANTS
(research, public authorities, advisors, business, rural communities, other EU-funded projects, etc.)

33 COUNTRIES

PRESENTATIONS AND
RECORDING [HERE](#)

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If you see this icon, click to see the presentation

If you see this icon, click to see the video

CODECS' Vision of Digital Ecosystems

Gianluca Brunori
University of Pisa & CODECS Coordinator

CODECS coordinator from the University of Pisa, **Gianluca Brunori** presented **CODECS vision of digital ecosystems** and their role in the current phase of digitalisation. He highlighted that innovation arises from the **assemblage of different components, including devices, software, databases, people, infrastructure, and sensors**. Using the example of smart tractors, he pointed out how they now collect data in addition to harvesting crops, thus transforming them into different machines than in the past.

He emphasised that **successful digitalisation occurs when all components of a digital ecosystem work together effectively**, and when the connections between these components are robust and allow for easy use. Crucially, digitalisation must also contribute to sustainable development goals.

Professor Brunori stressed that **innovation now depends on the cooperation between items, with each item needing to communicate and exchange data**. He also noted that technology needs to be combined with effective service design and business models, requiring a shift from technology as an object to technology as a service, supported by appropriate business models.

Governance and cooperation are key aspects of digital ecosystems, and policies can support the development of conducive digital environments. He concluded by stating that the aim of CODECS is to identify specific pathways for successful digital ecosystems.

Figure 1. CODECS' current phase of digital transformation

Policy Pathways for Inclusive Digital Access in Agriculture

Doris Marquardt
DG CONNECT, European Commission

Doris Marquardt from the European Commission's Directorate-General for Communications Network, Content and Technology (DG CNECT) discussed **policy pathways for inclusive digital access in agriculture**. She emphasised that digital transformation processes need to be sustainable and inclusive in themselves.

Marquardt noted that the European Commission aims to make Europe a global leader in Artificial Intelligence (AI) innovation, while also ensuring trust, security, and respect for fundamental rights, especially within agriculture.

She outlined several **challenges to achieving inclusive digital access** which goes beyond just connectivity. These include a lack of trust, a limited number of actors with sufficient data for AI applications, and a limited number of providers of decision-making support tools. To overcome these, she highlighted the development of a **common European agriculture data space to make data available for innovators and other parties**, as well as to reduce the cost for farmers to benefit from tailored digital applications.

Mrs Marquardt presented key policy initiatives, including the **2030 Digital Decade targets**, the **Data Act**, and the **AI Act**, designed to foster trust in AI technologies, and mentioned support programs like **Horizon Europe** and the **Connecting Europe Facility** and the **Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)** which also contribute to digitalisation of the agricultural sector.

She drew attention to the **Data Act** which will enter into force in September 2025, and aims to empower all businesses to have the capacity to negotiate fair data-sharing contracts. She stressed that it would allow farmers to have data sovereignty and to be in control of with whom they share their data.

Figure 2. Key components of the Data Act. Source: European Commission (2024)

Doris Marquardt emphasised that there is no one-size-fits-all approach to inclusive digitalisation, and socioeconomic conditions must be considered. **Effective digital access** requires not only infrastructure, but also human capacities, trust, demonstration projects, and data. Mrs Marquardt stressed that innovation **should consider social, cultural, legal, economic, and environmental conditions**. She noted the importance of capacity building and networking to bring together end-users (farmers) and innovators. She noted that data and AI-based solutions are increasingly important for digital transformation. She concluded by stating that policy instruments, including regulatory and supporting instruments, are directly and indirectly facilitating inclusive digital access in agriculture.

Digital Ecosystems: Definitions and Frameworks

Cynthia Giagnocavo
University of Almería

Cynthia Giagnocavo from the University of Almeria presented [CODECS' report for analysing digital ecosystems \(2024\)](#). A digital ecosystem is a “dynamic system with digital, socio-economic, organisational, knowledge, and physical components that converge to support the production, storage, communication, and utilisation of digital technologies and data”. Professor Giagnocavo stressed the importance of understanding **sustainable digitalisation** and moving beyond a technology-centered approach as the sole answer, but rather focusing on the social, ecological, and organisational aspects of digital transformation.

She described a framework based on **socio-ecological systems** as developed by Eleanor Ostrum, focusing on actors, governance, resource systems, and resources within the focal action situation. This framework helps to analyse how various subsystems enable or hinder resources and capabilities needed for sustainable digitalisation at farm level. Cynthia explained that the approach is to use **organisational studies of resources and capabilities** to understand how different subsystems enable the resources and capabilities that actors need to solve their problems.

They led **workshops with CODECS Living Labs (LLs)** to identify their resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations. They considered how various subsystems foster or hinder what is

needed to address the problems stated in the focal action situation, seeking to identify the specific characteristics that make digital ecosystems conducive for sustainable agriculture.

She concluded her presentation by sharing **key findings across the different LLs**, from the analysis of the core subsystems:

- **Resource systems** face challenges with internet infrastructure, inflexible financial systems, a lack of standardised data systems, inefficient knowledge sharing, and data storage issues.
- **Governance systems** may introduce new dynamics of shared responsibility in data management and knowledge exchange, as well as the tension between regulation and the dynamic nature of technology.
- For **actors**, there is an aging farming population with limited digital skills. She noted that technology providers were not always well integrated into the LLs and that collective action is important.
- Finally, the **resource units** need more innovative funding, tailored technology, and knowledgeable human resources, and they also need access to knowledge, storage, and information.

Figure 3. CODECS' Mapping of Digital Ecosystems of Living Labs, Conceptual framework (2024)

Living Labs Case Studies: Real-World Applications of Digital Ecosystems

The webinar included case studies from two of the CODECS Living Labs, showcasing real-world applications of digital ecosystems in agricultural settings.

Vojtěch Novák Czech University of Life Sciences in Prague Czech Living Lab – Automation of Orchard Management

Vojtěch Novák from the Czech University of Life Sciences in Prague presented the work of the [Czech Living Lab](#), which focuses on the automated management of orchards.

The main problems the lab addresses include **water management and the optimisation of water usage in orchards**. They are also measuring environmental parameters and building a digital twin of the orchard environment.

The LL aims to monitor effective radiation management, and other factors that emerge during their experiments. They use **Internet of Thing (IoT) sensors** to measure parameters like humidity, temperature, and soil moisture. The data is measured every 10 minutes and includes around 50 parameters from the orchard, providing real-time information useful for analysis and decision-making. Data is also collected through scientific equipment to create data layers, such as soil conductivity for example.

Furthermore, the lab also uses **drones with RGB (Red, Green, and Blue), multispectral, and thermal cameras** to create data layers about the trees, which helps to calculate tree size, spacing, and health.

The **data is then analysed**, and discussions with farmers help to confirm the accuracy of the measurements and inform decisions. For example, data analysis could help farmers decide which trees to replace. The data collected is transferred to a data platform, where it becomes available for scientific and other uses.

Figure 4. CZU dashboard for the analysis of temperature in the orchard

Mario Petkovski AgFutura Technologies Macedonian Living Lab – RAMAS

Mario Petkovski from AG Futura Technologies presented the [Macedonian Living Lab](#) and its remote agricultural monitoring and advisory system (RAMAS).

Located in a grapevine production area, RAMAS is designed to support decision-making in agricultural production through **advisory services** based on data collected from the field at each phase of production. The system aims to address challenges in implementing digital and precision technologies in agriculture, considering the diversity of farms.

The main objectives of the system are to: create a model for a centralised advisory system, increase communication between farmers and advisors, optimise agricultural inputs and processes, increase the effectiveness of decision-making, improve farm accounting, and collect data on agrotechnical operations.

The main problems it seeks to solve include limited agricultural professional support, a lack of farm accountancy and agrotechnical data, non-optimised agricultural production processes, and energy inefficiency. The platform stores data, improves communication, and supports the implementation of digital technologies, with the goal of optimising agricultural production, reducing costs, and enhancing productivity and sustainability.

RAMAS functions as a data centre which collects data from the farm and farmer opinions, which are then sent to a data analysis centre. The **analysed data is then used to create advisory services** that are sent back to the farmers. A collaboration layer is also used to calibrate the system and the agricultural production system. The system is currently a semi-functional web application being tested, with a focus on improving visibility and user experience.

The core components of the RAMAS Living Lab include the **RAMAS platform**, the implementation of precision and **digital agriculture technologies**, **agribusiness development** strategies, a **data repository**, **farm management tools**, and **decision-making support for farmers**. The platform provides various types of data, such as productivity maps, soil pH distribution, and UAV (unmanned aerial vehicles)-generated data.

Petkovski highlighted that RAMAS is unique due to its **technological integration and flexibility**. It also provides consistent and high-quality expertise, a centralised digital infrastructure, and economic benefits for the farm. The system has six customisable programs and a cost-effective **model that adapts to the farm size and complexity**, and it also offers strategic support to farms in developing their business models to improve agricultural production systems.

Figure 5. Core components of RAMAS Living Lab

Source: Freepik

Group discussion

Moderator by Serafin Pazos-Vidal (AEIDL)

The presentations were followed by a discussion, where participants had the opportunity to raise questions and comments to speakers. Moderated by **Serafin Pazos-Vidal** from CODECS partner AEIDL, the interaction raised several key points regarding digital ecosystems in agriculture, and the challenges and opportunities they present.

One of the primary topics of discussion was the **practical application of data and digital technologies in farming**. A question was raised about how a decision support system translates the large amount of collected data into actionable steps for farmers. In response, it was explained that the system aims to provide simple action-oriented advice, rather than burdening farmers with complex data analysis. The system is designed to communicate directly with the farmers, offering specific recommendations, such as the type and amount of fertiliser needed for different zones of their farm. The cost of such a system is customised based on the complexity and size of the farm.

Another point of discussion was **the use of AI for data analysis**. It was highlighted that while machine learning is currently used for certain tasks, such as UAV surveillance for example, there is an intention to implement AI in the future, for example as a chatbot to provide farmers with an immediate response to their questions.

Additionally, when discussing the **way forward for Living Labs**, it was noted that many variables (including regulation and market

changes) make it difficult to have a clear path ahead. Their aim is to create a framework for people and farmers to articulate their issues and understand the different systems they are dealing with.

The discussion also touched on the **issue of power imbalances**, with some big players controlling much of the data, and potentially using it against farmers. In order to fix this issue, speakers highlighted the importance of making the risks and benefits of data-sharing feasible for farmers. For instance, building data cooperatives can help deal with these issues of trust and governance.

Finally, there was a **call for the better implementation of Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) to support farmers**. It was suggested that the focus of digitalisation should move from the capacity of farmers to adopt technologies, to the services provided to farmers through these technologies. It was also noted that there needs to be a stronger layer of intermediaries to design such services, and that a stronger network of advisors and data integrators is crucial. Moreover, speakers highlighted that existing public databases are not always interoperable, and there are language and semantic barriers to integrating data. It was argued that the debate should move to how to **provide better services to farmers**, and that digital ecosystems are key to making such services available. Data spaces, that allow data to move between providers, are necessary. Moreover, there are significant barriers to the digitalisation of data, which should be addressed by policy.

Conclusions & next steps

Merveille Ntabuhashe
AEIDL

In conclusion, this event highlighted the critical importance of a holistic and collaborative approach to digital transformation in agriculture. **The key takeaways from the presentations and discussions include the need for integrated digital ecosystems that combine technology with social, economic, and organisational factors.** The emphasis is on moving beyond technology-centric solutions to address the full complexity of sustainable digitalisation.

The webinar underscored the importance of data sharing, interoperability, and building trust among stakeholders. The role of effective policy, capacity building, and knowledge sharing were also highlighted as essential to achieving inclusive and sustainable digitalisation in the agricultural sector.

In her concluding remarks, Merveille Ntabuhashe from AEIDL, highlighted that this event was organised in the framework of **CODECS Knowledge Accelerator (KA)**. The KA Community is a space for stakeholders to discuss issues related to sustainable digitalisation of agriculture. The goal is to involve a variety of actors (including farmers, advisors, and policymakers) to identify effective strategies for sustainable digitalisation. Interested actors can register to **join CODECS Knowledge Accelerator Community**.

